

brat

 Universität Trier

Guidelines for Annotating Argumentative Discourse Units on Speeches extracted from the Europarl Corpus

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1. Introduction

Within the context of this thesis, an automated Argument Mining Process on french and german speeches taken from the Europarl Corpus containing proceedings of the European Parliament between 1996 and 2011 will be implemented and analyzed. Argument Mining is the automated extraction of structured, natural-language arguments from unstructured text data. As a supervised Machine Learning task, the algorithm first needs human-made labels to be trained on. To put it simply, data is needed on whether a text passage is argumentative or not. The task of creating these labels, annotation, requires a basic understanding of what an argument looks like, how argument components interact and how to resolve cases of ambiguity. The more the annotators agree in their assessments, the clearer the picture for the algorithm to learn will be. To provide the annotator with necessary instructions, the following guidelines will accompany you throughout the annotation process. The pages ahead will give you a quick, yet thorough overview on the annotation workflow. Anyway, your work is very much appreciated. Have fun annotating!

2. Argumentative Discourse Units

This section describes Argumentative Discourse Units (ADU) and how to find them. Arguments are used either for logical inference of one own's opinion or to persuade others. The data to be assessed are of political nature since they result from speeches in the European Parliament. As a consequence, the person to establish the argument is a speaker and the people to receive the argument are deputies. An argument in its simplest form consists of two different units: one claim and at least one premise.

Claims are the conclusion the speaker seeks to establish by his speech. In the political context, the claim is the one sentence in a paragraph containing the main message. It is decision-relevant, action-driven information to which one can have a positive or negative stance. In figure 1 below, the last sentence, the demand to promote multilateral conventions, is the claim. Starting with "*deshalb*" (therefore), the sentence contains the main message of the paragraph, shows a clear intention (promotion of conventions) and is related to an action (signing the treaties) with which you can agree or disagree (should the treaties be signed or not).

A claim always needs one or more accompanying **premises** to form an argument. Without adequate reasoning, a sentence does not qualify as a claim and is a non-argumentative statement at most. Hence, premises add the persuasion to the message. A premise provides the evidence and reasoning to support the claim. Premises specify the claim through examples, reasons and justifications or highlight its importance by rhetorical devices. In this manner, premises come in two flavors: the direct, supporting premise and the indirect rebuttal. A rebuttal delivers a counterevidence which has the rhetorical function to be undermined to further strengthen the claim. Generally, premises build up a logical chain. If you take a look at figure 1, you see four sentences identified as premises. Sentence one and two show how the role of the EU solidified (=premise). Then sentence three underlines the EU's importance (=premise). Sentence four leads to new challenges (=premise) before the claim is finally presented.

Figure 1: ADUs of an argument.

Now that we know what claims and premises are, we need to consider how they are arranged in a political argument. To this purpose, we distinguish two common patterns: expert opinion style and judgement style. The standard case is expert opinion style where premises occur previously to the claim. Figure 2 illustrates an argument in expert opinion style. The premises building a logical chain come first, followed by a conclusion introduced by the claim indicator "*darum*" (due to).

Figure 2: Expert opinion style.

The exact opposite order of claims and premises is used in judgement style. Here, the claim is the introducing statement which is followed by a collection of reasons as can be seen in figure 3. Both styles are common in political speeches, but there are also some exceptions due to linguistic variations. Thus, a claim can also appear in the second sentence or in the middle of an argument.

Figure 3: Judgement style

3. Using the brat annotation tool: how to start

The foundations in mind, 15 speeches per person have to be edited. To access and work with the speeches, the brat annotation tool will be used. Here is how to get started:

1. Access www.annotating-speech.eu from chrome or safari.

2. Click 'ok' on the brat welcome window.

3. In the collection browser, choose the language you will be annotating in and confirm.

4. Select your user directory (in case you received the user "german_annotator1" you click on "german_annotator1") and confirm.

5. Select the speech you want to annotate by clicking on it and confirm.

- Now you already see the speech but still need to log in with your credentials to gain editing rights, therefore move your mouse towards the brat icon and push the login button.

- Then, you need to login with your username and password which you received in the previous mail.

4. Using the brat annotation tool: making annotations

To annotate a text span you drag the mouse over it. Only sentences should be marked as claims or premises. A sentence starts with the first word and ends with the last word before the full stop. Colons and Semicolons can be ignored. An easy abbreviation is pressing **CTRL** and double-clicking the first word of the sentence and then pressing **SHIFT** and clicking at the last word of the sentence.

To select whether the marked sentence is a claim or a premise you can either click on the category in the annotation pane or simply use the keyboard shortcuts **P** for premise or **C** for claim.

To navigate between speeches you simply use the arrows on the top left corner of the screen or the **arrow keys**. Your changes will be saved automatically. Further informations on the usage of brat can be found in the [official user manual](#).

On the next page, you find an overview on the annotation workflow. It is recommended to leave the page open to look up the definitions as you go.

5. Workflow Cheat Sheet

Step 1: As a first step, you skim over the speech. Make sure you understand the context and what it generally is about.

Step 2: Read the first argument. Usually, an argument is as long as one paragraph. Therefore, paragraphs are a useful orientation. Judge, whether the paragraph is argumentative at all using this working definition:

Argumentative:

A text should be seen as **argumentative** if you think that it explicitly or implicitly conveys the *stance* of the speaker on some *controversial* issue. (Wachsmuth 2017)

- Not argumentative are official welcomes and farewells, acknowledgements, summaries of current events, reporting passages and enumerations, transition sentences and pure statements without reasons.

Step 3: If the paragraph is argumentative, mark a claim. Please, always mark complete sentences ending with a full stop. (Reminder: the claim is typically positioned at the beginning or the end of a paragraph)

Claim:

The **conclusion** we seek to establish by our arguments. (Freeley 1961)

- Which sentence reflects the main message of the argument?
- has a stance which can be shared or not
- related to an action or demand in need of justification
- german claim indicators: „dementsprechend“, „folglich“, „infolge“, „zu dem Schluss kommen“, „zeigt, dass“, „es erforderlich machen“, „daher“, „also“, „impliziert“, „meiner Meinung nach“, „schlussendlich“, „abschließend“, „ich glaube“, „ich denke“, „es ist meine Überzeugung“, „deshalb“, „deswegen“, „ich schlage vor“, „daraus können wir schließen“, „aus diesen Gründen“

Step 4: Having identified the claim, mark at least one premise, supporting or attacking the claim by using one of the two definitions below. As with the claims, please always mark complete sentences ending with a full stop.

Premise (support):

Evidence and reasoning advanced to *establish* the foundation of a claim. (Freeley 1961)

Premise (rebuttal):

Evidence or reasoning advanced to *weaken* or *destroy* another's claim. (Freeley 1961)

OR

- Which sentences support the claim, be it through evidence, rhetorical or through the refutation of a counterargument?
- premises specify, justify or highlight importance
- the first premise can be the beginning of the logical inference chain or the sentence following the claim in judgement style
- german premise indicators: „trotz“, „angenommen, dass“, „gesetzt, dass“, „wie Sie am folgenden Beispiel erkennen“, „wie das Beispiel zeigt“, „zunächst“, „außerdem“, „aufgrund“, „zum Beispiel“, „des Weiteren“, „angesichts“, „unterstützt durch“, „wegen“, „Forscher fanden heraus“, „erstens“, „zweitens“, „wohingegen“, „so zum Beispiel“, „übrigens“, „nehmen wir“, „das heißt“

Overview:

6. Troubleshooting and Best Practices

What is there to do in case of uncertainty? As argument annotation is a subjective task that depends on viewpoints. There might be situations when you are not entirely sure whether the chosen annotation is correct. To deal with this issue, this section provides you with some best practices. First, you check if your problem is listed below. Else, you can leave a note or check the *german_annotator0*-directory in brat to see an already annotated version of the speeches.

Figure 4: Leaving a note when uncertain.

Scenario 1: The task is to highlight sentences only. What should be done if an ADU is only taking up a few words or a subordinate clause?

In case, a claim or premise is occupying less space than the length of a sentence, mark each sentence that contains a claim or premise. If a premise is not fitting in the sentence because it is longer than one sentence, mark the sentence that is part of the larger premise. Finally, should it be the case that a sentence contains both a claim AND a premise, choose the claim because it is the argument's essence. The latter is illustrated in figure 5 with the last sentence of the argument containing premises (reduce risks, enhance resistance, support developing countries) and a claim (taking measurements), whereof the claim is chosen. Additionally, arguments consisting of only one marked sentence become thereby possible.

Figure 5: If a claim and a premise are in the same sentence, choose the claim.

Scenario 2: Several sentences in the paragraph are good claim candidates. Which one should be chosen?

To resolve this ambiguity, a recursive technique to identify claims is proposed. Is the first sentence of the claim a potential argumentative statement, mark it as claim. Is the subsequent sentence a deduction thereof, replace the previous sentence with the current one as the claim. Continue until you have reached the end of the paragraph. In order to test if a sentence is a deduction check if the sentence contains a claim indicator such as "daher" or "deshalb" or if you could insert such an indicator without the sentence changing its meaning. Is the situation still unclear, maybe due to several sentences with a similar content, try if the meaning of the paragraph changes after you leave the sentence out to test the sentence's importance. If you follow this claim hierarchy, you are guaranteed to receive exactly one claim per argument.

Figure 6: Mark and replace claim candidates until you reach the end of the logical inference.

Scenario 3: *More background knowledge is needed to grasp the context of the speech.*

Sometimes, the annotator who is no professional translator or deputy of the European Parliament needs further information. Luckily the annotation is conducted online, hence, there are plenty of possibilities. Should a word be unknown especially in the french annotation, the german translation can be opened in a new tab just by using the word search function. This can easily be accessed by double-clicking the unknown word and then selecting the FR-GER link in the annotation window. Similarly, some simple background checking is possible. When you are not convenient with some geopolitical vocabulary, you can open the corresponding Wikipedia page just by double-clicking and then selecting the Wikipedia link.

Figure 7: Word Search.

If you are still not sure what to do with some text passages, if there is a technical issue, if you have any questions, suggestions or if there simply is some room for discussion, you can always contact me via mail s4frgraf@uni-trier.de or call me under 004915254171039.